

Metabolomics Profiling of Cigarette Smoke-Exposed Wistar Rat Lungs by ATR-FTIR Spectroscopy, and Mass Spectrometry Revealed Important Theranostics Metabolites Using Inhaled Cysteamine Nanoemulsions

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Groups	Abbreviation(s) used	Number of Biological replicates
Normal Control	NC	3
Diseased control/ Cigarette smoke induced COPD	DC/COPD	5
Plain cysteamine given orally	CPO	5
Cysteamine nanoemulsions given orally	CFO	5
Cysteamine nanoemulsions given <i>via</i> inhalation	CFI	5
Total		23